

Enhancing transversal competencies through PBL: insights from peer and self-assessment

Lílian Barros Pereira Campos^{1,2}, Roger Junio Campos², Janaina Antonino Pinto^{1,3}, Tatiana Gesteira de Almeida Ferraz⁴, Camila de Sousa Pereira⁴

¹ Grupo MAES – Grupo de Pesquisa em Metodologias Ativas do Ensino Superior, Federal University of Itajubá – Itabira Campus, Itabira, Minas Gerais, Brazil

² Federal University of Itajubá – Itabira Campus, Itabira, Minas Gerais, Brazil

³ LALT – Laboratório de Aprendizagem em Logística e Transporte, Universidade Estadual de Campinas, Campinas, Brazil

⁴ Senai/CIMATEC, Salvador, Brazil

Email: liliancampos@unifei.edu.br, rogercampos@unifei.edu.br, janainaantonino@unicamp.br, tatianaa@fieb.org.br, camila.pereira@fieb.org.br

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Abstract

The economic and social demands of the modern world present significant challenges in engineering education, requiring universities to prepare students for professional life. Therefore, it is essential to improve the teaching process to not only address the specific competencies of each engineering field but also develop transversal competencies. These transversal competencies should be integrated into the planning of teaching dynamics and learning assessment. This paper presents an experience with project-based learning (PBL) and transversal competence assessment involving 46 engineering students in an undergraduate Instrumentation course at the Federal University of Itajubá (Unifei) - Theodomiro Santiago campus in Itabira. The students worked in 12 teams to develop solutions to industrial or societal problems. Following the PBL experience, they conducted self and peer assessments of the transversal competencies demonstrated throughout the project. The Soft Skills Assessment System for Engineering Students (SACTEE) was used to assess both types of evaluations, tracking the development of competencies. The findings revealed that students struggled most with conflict mediation, learning from mistakes, willingness to assist colleagues, and fostering collaboration. In contrast, ethics and professionalism, as well as respect for differences, were the highest-rated competencies. These results suggest that such competencies can be better nurtured through intentional learning experiences designed by educators and institutions. This study emphasizes the value of collaborative activities, as they allow students to assess their peers and reflect on their development and contributions to others' growth, thus promoting self-management and leadership skills. The study is part of the "Development of Transversal Competencies (TC)" project, registered on the Brazil Platform (61376922.7.0000.5094).

Keywords: transversal competencies; Engineering Education; self-assessment; peer-assessment

1 Introduction

The new economic and social demands of the modern world present significant and real challenges in engineering education. Engineers face significant challenges when asked to create new technologies and innovations. Talks et al. (2014) argue that universities must take on the responsibility of training professionals who are ready to enter the workforce and be able to progress there. Therefore, engineering schools are confronted with the challenge of teaching specific skills (Ohland et al., 2004) as well as transversal competencies (TC) (Torres et al., 1997). Mitchell, Skinner, and White (2010) understand that TCs can be seen as interpersonal qualities, which in the literature are sometimes referred to as soft skills.

In Brazil, The National Curriculum Guidelines, especially in Engineering, have pointed to the need for higher education institutions to assist students in their specific self-development according to their area of expertise, as well as in their human self-development, regarding generic competencies such as communication, innovation, creativity, among others. In this context, the project titled "Development of Transversal Competencies in Engineering" was created, registered on the Plataforma Brasil with the Ethical Appreciation Presentation Certificate number 61376922.7.0000.5094. These transversal competencies should be integrated

into the planning of teaching dynamics and learning assessment using active learning such as PBL (Problem Based Learning). The PBL is a form of situational learning based on the constructivist findings where the student gains a profound comprehension when he or she gets involved in their knowledge development (Krajcik & Blumenfeld, 2006). This approach has been gaining ground especially in applied science universities due to the student's necessity to develop several learning competencies for the professional environment. It is a technique that provides multifaceted learning experiences as opposed to the traditional teaching method (Lettenmeier, Autio, & Jänis, 2014)

This paper presents an experience with project-based learning (PBL) and transversal competence assessment involving 46 engineering students in an undergraduate Instrumentation course at the Federal University of Itajubá (Unifei) - Theodomiro Santiago campus in Itabira. The students worked in 12 teams to develop solutions to industrial or societal problems. Following the PBL experience, they conducted self and peer assessments of the transversal competencies demonstrated throughout the project. The Soft Skills Assessment System for Engineering Students (SACTEE) was used to assess both types of evaluations, tracking the development of competencies.

2 Transversal Competencies in Engineering Education

In the literature, it can be found a list of several transversal competencies engineers must have, such as communication, creativity, innovation, adaptability, organisation, problem-solving, resilience, proactivity, teamwork among others (Souza & Campos, 2019). In this context, engineering students must be supported, not only in the development of their technical competencies, but also in the improvement of their soft skills.

García-Alvarez et al. (2022) showed a systematic review of the transversal competencies for employability in university graduates from an employer's perspective. They concluded that higher education institutions should adopt pedagogies for employability to strengthen the connection between academic learning and the socio-professional context, thereby facilitating a smoother and more effective transition of graduates into the workforce. Belchior-Rocha et al. (2022) identified the perception of recent graduates as to the importance of the transversal skills that they acquired and developed at university and the ways in which they are now applied in the work environment.

The transversal competencies are increasingly used by engineering professionals who are looking for professionals with skills beyond technical expertise, capable of working in multidisciplinary environments and with a high capacity for adaptation. Traditional training, focused on the transmission of content, has been insufficient for the development of these skills, making it urgent to adopt pedagogical practices that favor more integrated and collaborative experiences.

3 PBL: Project Based Learning in Engineering Courses

The active Project Based Learning (PBL) methodology is a student-centered pedagogical approach in which knowledge is constructed through the investigation and resolution of complex problems, usually linked to real-world situations. According to Thomas (2000), PBL involves a central project as an organizing structure for the teaching-learning process, promoting student engagement and protagonism. Projects are challenging, multidisciplinary and require the application of diverse knowledge for their completion, creating a more authentic and meaningful learning environment. Lima et al. (2017) showed that active learning engages and challenges students using real-life and imaginary situations where students engage in such higher-order thinking tasks as analysis, synthesis and evaluation.

The application of Project Based Learning (PBL) in engineering has proven essential to align academic training with the demands of the professional market, which requires engineers with integrated technical skills and interpersonal competencies. This methodology allows students to face real engineering problems, promoting the development of skills such as logical reasoning, decision-making, leadership, teamwork and effective communication. According to Hernández-de-Menéndez et al. (2019), PBL provides more active and contextualized learning, allowing students to understand the applicability of theoretical content in practical situations. The use of PBL in engineering courses contributes to the development of students' autonomy and capacity for innovation, making them better prepared to deal with complex challenges in multidisciplinary and technologically advanced environments (Shinde and Kolmos, 2011; Askehave et al., 2015).

In the context of transversal skills – such as communication, empathy, problem-solving, leadership and teamwork – PBL has proven to be particularly effective. The collaborative nature of the projects encourages interaction between students, promoting the development of interpersonal and socio-emotional skills. Furthermore, by working with integrative and relevant themes, PBL favors interdisciplinarity and contextualization of teaching, strengthening the link between theory and practice and preparing students for the challenges of personal, academic and professional life (Lima et al., 2017; Hernández-de-Menéndez et al., 2019).

4 Study Context

Project-Based Learning (PBL) was the chosen pedagogical approach for the implementation of a hands-on, real-world learning experience at the Federal University of Itajubá (UNIFEI), located in Itabira - Minas Gerais, Brazil. This strategy was chosen to promote active learning through the investigation and resolution of real-life problems, fostering the development of essential competencies for students' professional formation. Additionally, the adoption of PBL aimed to make the learning process more dynamic and engaging, bridging the gap between theoretical knowledge and practical application.

The project was conducted within a technical discipline that is part of the sixth-semester curriculum for students enrolled in the Electrical Engineering and Control and Automation Engineering programs. This course comprises approximately 90 hours (64 theoretical and 32 practical), with a significant portion of the practical classes held in the instrumentation laboratory.

The central objective of the project was to solve a real-world problem through the design and assembly of a sensor-based system for signal conditioning. Students were tasked with developing an electrical signal conditioning circuit that outputs signals within the 0 to 5 Volt range—standard in industrial applications—requiring the mandatory use of at least one sensor. The final prototype had to be delivered on a prototyped electronic board, with signal conditioning achieved using operational amplifiers.

Students were organized into groups of five, each led by a designated group leader to simulate a company-like structure with defined roles, responsibilities, and operational rules. Throughout the semester, students engaged in collaborative and practical activities, applying theoretical concepts in a problem-solving context. They conducted research, participated in discussions, and overcame challenges related to circuit design and system integration, enhancing their problem-solving skills, critical thinking, and creativity.

The culmination of the project involved presenting the developed prototype as if launching a commercial product, in front of a review panel composed of professors and industry professionals. The project accounted for 25% of the final course grade, with additional assessment components including written tests (45%), exercises (20%), and group seminars on specific content topics (10%).

Project evaluation considered several criteria: (i) peer collaboration, measured through four peer-assessment rounds during the semester; (ii) functionality of the final prototype; (iii) quality of the final written report; and (iv) effectiveness of the final presentation. The distribution of the 25 credits assigned to the project is shown in Table 1.

Table 1. Distribution of the 25 credits assigned to the project

Aspects assessed in the project	Percentage of project credits
Peer assessment	10%
Functional prototype	40%
Final paper	20%
Presentation	20%
TOTAL	100% ≡ 25 credits

In this course, students developed a variety of innovative projects, including a voltage harmonics meter, anti-sleep glasses, a smart irrigation system for monitoring temperature and humidity (smart ground), an oximeter, an automatic fire detection and extinguishing system, an automated greenhouse with control mechanisms to maintain basic environmental parameters, a decibel meter, an automatic curtain, and a position control system using an ultrasonic sensor.

5 Materials and Method

This research was conducted within the scope of the project titled "Development of Transversal Competencies in Engineering," which aims to identify favorable conditions for the development of transversal competencies (TC) among engineering students. Through a proposal for adopting the Plan-Do-Check-Act cycle applied to the development of TCs, this project has been used to assess the effectiveness of active learning strategies (Campos & Pinto, 2023a), the impact of different feedback modalities in remote teaching (Campos & Pinto, 2023b), and to clarify the TCs expected from engineers in training (Pinto, Campos & Lima Jr, 2024).

Considering the perspective of Prodanov and Freitas (2013), this research is characterized as basic in terms of its results, since the results help researchers understand the phenomenon. In terms of its objective, this research can be considered descriptive, as it will enable the description of how the investigated phenomenon occurs within the scope of the research. The problem approach is quantitative, as data collection on self-assessment and peer assessment of engineering students' TCs was carried out through a survey method.

The data collection instrument was the Transversal Competencies Evaluation Questionnaire (QuACT) in the Self-Assessment and Peer Assessment Scales of the Transversal Competencies Assessment System for Engineering Students (SACTEE), developed by Ferraz (2023). It is a data collection instrument suitable for the present study due to its psychometric quality, content validity, internal consistency, and replicability potential (FERRAZ, 2023).

The QuACT proposes the evaluation of 23 TCs, as described in the theoretical framework. The students were sent an Excel form through which they performed both their self-assessment and the peer assessment of their colleagues. For each TC assessed, students had to fill out a table considering their perception of the abilities demonstrated by themselves and their teammates. Thus, students were asked to select a score from 0 to 5 for their perception of the demonstration of each TC, where 0 = Not observed during the period; 1 = Barely developed; 2 = Slightly developed; 3 = Moderately developed; 4 = Well developed; and 5 = Very well developed.

The data were consolidated in spreadsheets and analyzed based on the frequency of responses at each level (0 to 5) for each question. The next section presents and discusses the results of the self-assessment and peer assessment of the TCs demonstrated by the students.

6 Results and Discussion

Based on the collected data, analyses were conducted using both student self-assessments and peer assessments. The data were aggregated to generate insights and reflections on the group of students who participated in the experience.

Among the 56 students enrolled in the analyzed group, 82% completed the questionnaire. However, only responses from teams with at least three participants were considered valid, as each team consisted of up to five members. This criterion was established to ensure that peer assessments were representative of each team. In total, 46 valid responses were included in the self-assessment analysis, while 172 responses were considered for the peer assessment.

Table 2 displays the frequency of responses by TC across the self-assessment and peer-assessment scales. To enhance visual interpretation, conditional formatting was applied in Excel: cells are shaded in red to indicate lower frequencies and in green to indicate higher frequencies.

Table 2. Frequency of responses by scale level in the self-assessment (n = 46) and peer assessment (n = 172)

#	Central Aspect Assessed	Frequency of Responses - Self-Assessment (%)					Frequency of Responses - Peer-Assessment (%)						
		0	1	2	3	4	5	0	1	2	3	4	5
Q1	Identification of critical points for the work	0%	0%	0%	4%	22%	67%	1%	1%	2%	8%	17%	71%
Q2	Expression of creativity	0%	0%	0%	11%	17%	65%	1%	1%	1%	7%	22%	69%
Q3	Argumentation skills	0%	0%	0%	7%	24%	63%	1%	1%	2%	3%	24%	69%
Q4	Persistence	0%	0%	0%	9%	13%	72%	1%	1%	1%	6%	18%	73%
Q5	Adaptability	2%	0%	0%	2%	15%	74%	1%	1%	1%	2%	21%	74%
Q6	Autonomous learning	0%	0%	2%	4%	24%	63%	1%	1%	1%	4%	20%	73%
Q7	Willingness to help colleagues	0%	0%	0%	7%	30%	57%	3%	0%	2%	8%	22%	66%
Q8	Proactivity	0%	0%	0%	9%	28%	57%	1%	1%	2%	4%	24%	68%
Q9	Attendance	0%	0%	0%	7%	22%	65%	1%	0%	2%	6%	15%	76%
Q10	Meeting deadlines	0%	0%	0%	4%	17%	72%	1%	1%	2%	2%	17%	77%
Q11	Respect for differences	2%	0%	0%	0%	4%	85%	1%	0%	0%	0%	5%	92%
Q12	Collaboration with the group	0%	0%	0%	0%	15%	78%	1%	1%	1%	1%	17%	79%
Q13	Ethics and professionalism	0%	0%	0%	0%	15%	78%	1%	1%	1%	0%	9%	90%
Q14	Collective construction of solutions	0%	0%	0%	2%	15%	76%	3%	0%	1%	5%	16%	75%
Q15	Encouragement of collaboration	2%	0%	2%	9%	20%	61%	3%	1%	1%	8%	21%	66%
Q16	Recognition for contributions	0%	0%	2%	4%	17%	70%	2%	0%	3%	0%	16%	79%
Q17	Written communication	0%	0%	2%	4%	11%	76%	3%	1%	1%	3%	17%	74%
Q18	Assertiveness	0%	0%	0%	9%	17%	67%	2%	1%	2%	6%	15%	74%
Q19	Active listening	0%	0%	0%	2%	15%	76%	2%	0%	1%	2%	16%	80%
Q20	Public oral communication	0%	0%	2%	7%	26%	59%	1%	1%	2%	5%	19%	72%
Q21	Conflict mediation within the group	9%	0%	0%	7%	17%	61%	9%	0%	1%	3%	17%	70%
Q22	Learning based on recognizing one's own mistakes	7%	0%	0%	0%	28%	59%	6%	1%	1%	4%	24%	65%
Q23	Openness to receiving criticism and feedback	0%	0%	0%	0%	20%	74%	1%	1%	0%	3%	21%	74%

In the self-assessment, the competencies (CTs) that received the highest frequency of 5 responses were: "Q11 - Respect for differences," "Q12 - Collaboration with the group," and "Q13 - Ethics and professionalism," with 85%, 78%, and 78%, respectively. In the peer assessment, the items that received the highest frequency of 5 responses were: "Q11 - Respect for differences," "Q13 - Ethics and professionalism," and "Q19 - Active listening," with 92%, 90%, and 80%, respectively. These results indicate the TCs that students perceived as being well or very well developed. For better visualization of the differences in the perception of development for each TC, Figure 1 presents a graph with the percentages of students who, in the self-assessment, answered 5, indicating the frequency with which the TC was very well developed.

Figure 1: Self-assessment result - percentage of students (n = 46) who answered 5 (very well developed) per TC

Label: Q1 - Identification of critical points for the work; Q2 - Expression of creativity; Q3 - Argumentation skills; Q4 – Persistence; Q5 – Adaptability; Q6 - Autonomous learning; Q7 - Willingness to help colleagues; Q8 – Proactivity; Q9 – Attendance; Q10 - Meeting deadlines; Q11 - Respect for differences; Q12 - Collaboration with the group; Q13 - Ethics and professionalism; Q14 - Collective construction of solutions; Q15 - Encouragement of collaboration; Q16 - Recognition for contributions; Q17 - Written communication; Q18 – Assertiveness; Q19 - Active listening; Q20 - Public oral communication; Q21 - Conflict mediation within the group; Q22 - Learning based on recognizing one’s own mistakes; Q23 - Openness to receiving criticism and feedback. Source: Authors, 2025.

On the other hand, the TC’s “Q22 - Learning based on recognizing one’s own mistakes”, “Q7 - Willingness to help colleagues” and “Q8 - Proactivity” with lower or equal percentage than 59%. The frequency of responses 5 per TC is also presented in Figure 2, but now considering the perception of peers.

Figure 2: Peer review result - percentage of students (n = 46) who answered 5 (very well developed) per TC

Label: Q1 - Identification of critical points for the work; Q2 - Expression of creativity; Q3 - Argumentation skills; Q4 – Persistence; Q5 – Adaptability; Q6 - Autonomous learning; Q7 - Willingness to help colleagues; Q8 – Proactivity; Q9 – Attendance; Q10 - Meeting deadlines; Q11 - Respect for differences; Q12 - Collaboration with the group; Q13 - Ethics and professionalism; Q14 - Collective construction of solutions; Q15 - Encouragement of collaboration; Q16 - Recognition for contributions; Q17 - Written communication; Q18 – Assertiveness; Q19 - Active listening; Q20 - Public oral communication; Q21 - Conflict mediation within the group; Q22 - Learning based on recognizing one’s own mistakes; Q23 - Openness to receiving criticism and feedback. Source: Authors, 2025.

When comparing the results of self-assessment and peer assessment, it can be seen that transversal competencies Q11 and Q13 had the same perception of being the most developed. In the opposite, the transversal competencies Q7 and Q22 had lower perception in both assessments. These data indicate that, although it is possible to identify common aspects to be worked on by engineering students in a comprehensive way (in more than one class or institution), other aspects may be more particular to certain people or groups, which reinforces the need for systematic evaluation of the transversal competencies.

7 Conclusion

The present paper offers important reflections on the development of transversal competencies (TCs) within the context of engineering education. This study provides references to support the selection of TCs to be developed by students, considering the diversity presented in the existing literature.

The research identified some TCs that students reported finding easier to apply in self-assessment and peer-assessment, such as respect for differences, acting with ethics and professionalism, and collaborating with the group. Collective construction of solutions and active listening also emerged as strengths in the individual and group assessments, respectively. However, one of the TCs students reported having the most difficulty was “learning based on recognizing one’s own mistakes”, in both types of assessments. This highlights the importance of self-awareness in developing the ability to understand that making mistakes can be a valuable part of the learning process. The application of the active methodology PBL also supports this, as it encourages students to reflect on mistakes and learn from them collaboratively. Students also mentioned proactiveness and willingness to help peers as relevant competencies. The PBL technique fosters more collaborative and proactive behaviors within the team, as project success depends on coordinated actions among the group members. These TCs can be better developed through learning experiences planned by both the educational institution and the course instructors.

However, this diagnosis should not be generalized, pointing to the need for a systematic evaluation of students’ TCs in higher education institutions, so that the development strategies for these competencies can be more effectively targeted. In this sense, the importance of collaborative activities is reinforced, as they offer a favorable environment in which students can evaluate their peers and reflect not only on their own self-development but also on their role in contributing to the development of others. This, in turn, fosters self-management and leadership growth. This study presents results from a research project in the field of engineering education. It followed best practices in educational research, including the use of robust data collection instruments developed from validated quality protocols and in accordance with the standards set by the Brazilian National Research Ethics Committee (CONEP).

References

- Askehave, I., Linnemann, H., Pedersen, J., & Pedersen, M. (2015). *Problem-based learning*. Aalborg.
- Belchior-Rocha, H., Casquilho-Martins, I., & Simões, E. (2022). Transversal competencies for employability: From higher education to the labour market. *Education Sciences*, 12(4), 255. <https://doi.org/10.3390/educsci12040255>
- Campos, L. B. P., & Pinto, J. A. (2023a). Skills development with a focus on self-awareness and self-management: The power is in the student’s hand. In 2023 International Conference on Active Learning in Engineering Education (PAEE/ALE) (pp. 103–111). PAEE/ALE.
- Campos, L. B. P., & Pinto, J. A. (2023b). Diferentes formatos de feedback para o desenvolvimento das habilidades transversais no ensino remoto: Uma experiência em cursos de engenharia. In IV Simpósio Internacional de Inovação em Educação Superior e IX Seminário Inovações em Atividades Curriculares: Desafios e perspectivas na Educação Superior. Espaço Ea2.
- Ferraz, T. G. A., & Pereira-Guizzo, C. S. (2023). Developing a system for assessing engineering students’ transferable skills: Evidence for the content validity and replicability of the scales. *European Journal of Engineering Education*, 48(4), 667–681. <https://doi.org/10.1080/03043797.2023.2174825>
- García-Álvarez, J., Vázquez-Rodríguez, A., Quiroga-Carrillo, A., & Priegue Caamaño, D. (2022). Transversal competencies for employability in university graduates: A systematic review from the employers’ perspective. *Education Sciences*, 12(3), 204. <https://doi.org/10.3390/educsci12030204>
- Hernández-de-Menéndez, M., Vallejo Guevara, A., Tudón Martínez, J. C., Hernández Alcántara, D., & Morales-Menendez, R. (2019). Active learning in engineering education: A review of fundamentals, best practices and experiences. *International Journal on Interactive Design and Manufacturing (IJIDeM)*, 13, 909–922. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12008-019-00557-8>
- Krajcik, J. S., & Blumenfeld, P. (2006). Project-based learning. In R. K. Sawyer (Ed.), *The Cambridge handbook of the learning sciences* (pp. 317–334). Cambridge University Press.
- Lettenmeier, M., Autio, S., & Jänis, R. (2014). Project-based learning on life-cycle management – A case study using material flow analysis. Retrieved from <https://www.lamk.fi/projektit/ecomill/ecomill-esilla/Documents/WRF-artikkeli%20Kulinaaritalo.pdf>
- Lima, R. M., Andersson, P. H., & Saalman, E. (2017). Active learning in engineering education: A (re)introduction. *European Journal of Engineering Education*, 42(1), 1–4. <https://doi.org/10.1080/03043797.2016.1254162>
- Mitchell, G. W., Skinner, L. B., & White, B. J. (2010). Essential soft skills for success in the twenty-first century workforce as perceived by business educators. *Delta Pi Epsilon Journal*, 52(1), 43–53.
- Pinto, J. A., Campos, L. B. P., & Lima Junior, O. F. (2024). Autoavaliação de competências transversais de estudantes de engenharia: Um estudo comparativo entre Unifei e Unicamp. In Anais do 10º Fórum STHEM, Brasília, DF. Sthem Brasil. <https://acesse.dev/sythK>
- Ohland, M. W., Frillman, S. A., & Miller III, T. K. (2004). NC State’s Engineering Entrepreneurs Program in the context of US education that works. In The NCIIA 8th Annual Meeting (pp. 155–164).
- Prodanov, C. C., & Freitas, E. C. (2013). *Metodologia do trabalho científico (recursos eletrônicos): Métodos e técnicas da pesquisa e do trabalho acadêmico* (2ª ed.). Feevale.

- Shinde, V., & Kolmos, A. (2011). Students' experience of Aalborg PBL model: A case study. In SEFI Annual Conference 2011 (pp. 197–204).
- Souza, A. S., & Campos, L. B. P. (2019). Habilidades transversais de engenheiros em formação: O papel de projetos de extensão. *Research, Society and Development*, 8(4), 32. <https://doi.org/10.33448/rsd-v8i4.652>
- Täks, M., Tynjälä, P., Toding, M., Kukemelk, H., & Venessar, U. (2014). Engineering students' experiences in studying entrepreneurship. *Journal of Engineering Education*, 103(4), 573–598. <https://doi.org/10.1002/jee.20054>
- Thomas, J. W. (2000). *A review of research on project-based learning*. San Rafael, CA: The Autodesk Foundation.
- Torres, M. A., Velez Arocho, J. I., & Pabon, J. A. (1997, November). BA 3100-Technology-based entrepreneurship: An integrated approach to engineering and business education. In Proceedings Frontiers in Education 1997 27th Annual Conference. Teaching and Learning in an Era of Change (Vol. 2, pp. 738–743). IEEE. <https://doi.org/10.1109/FIE.1997.635921>